

Isocoumarins: Part IV. Synthesis of some 3,4-dimethylisocoumarins

R. B. Telang and R. N. Usgaonkar

3,4-Dimethylisocoumarins have been synthesised by successfully cyclodehydrating α -methylacetyl esters of the following acids: α -resorcylic acid, its dimethyl ether, gallic acid, its trimethyl ether, 3-hydroxy and 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acids. Various reactions on these isocoumarins have been investigated. (\pm) 4,6-Dimethoxy- α -methylhomophthalic acid has been synthesised from 5,6-dimethoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin.

Synthesis of 5,7-dihydroxy, 5,7-dimethoxy-, 5,6,7-trihydroxy- and 5,6,7-trimethoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarins (IIa-d) and 5-hydroxy- and 5-methoxy-3,4,8-trimethylisocoumarins (IIe and f) has been achieved by a procedure similar to the one described in the earlier communication.^{1,2} α -Methylacetyl esters of the following acids: α -resorcylic acid, its dimethyl ether, gallic acid, its trimethyl ether, 3-hydroxy- and 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acids (Ia-f) were prepared in excellent yields by condensing the acids with 1-bromoethyl methyl ketone in presence of potassium carbonate. These esters cyclodehydrated in presence of 90% sulphuric acid to give the corresponding isocoumarins (IIa-f, respectively).

I

II

III

IV

- a, $R_1 = R_3 = \text{OH}$, $R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}$
- b, $R_1 = R_3 = \text{OMe}$, $R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}$
- c, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{OH}$, $R_4 = \text{H}$
- d, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{OMe}$, $R_4 = \text{H}$
- e, $R_1 = \text{OH}$, $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$, $R_4 = \text{Me}$
- f, $R_1 = \text{OMe}$, $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$, $R_4 = \text{Me}$

Cyclodehydration of the ester of α -resorcylic acid (Ia) and of that of its dimethyl ether (Ib) took place readily at room temperature to give the corresponding isocoumarins

1. H. K. Desai and R. N. Usgaonkar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 821.
2. R. B. Telang and R. N. Usgaonkar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (under publication)

IIa and IIb in an yield exceeding 90%. The competing reaction of hydrolysis of the ester to form the corresponding acid was practically not observed and the reaction was over within a short period of 3 hr. As a matter of fact, cyclodehydration in case of the ester Ia took place even at 0–5° and the yield at this temperature was better than at room temperature. In case of the esters of the other acids it was found necessary to keep the reaction mixture for a period varying from 24 to 48 hr. to get good yields. Cyclodehydration in presence of conc. H₂SO₄ was invariably accompanied with the competing reaction of hydrolysis of the ester to form the acid to more or less extent depending on the reactivity of the ester in the cyclodehydration. The more reactive the ester less was the acid formed. The yield of the isocoumarin (IIc) obtained from the ester of gallic acid (Ic) was good but that of the isocoumarin (IIId) from the ester of its trimethyl ether (Id) was poor. This may be attributed to the steric effect of the bulky—OMe group. Surprisingly the ester of 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid (If) gave a better yield of the isocoumarin than that obtained from the ester of the corresponding hydroxy acid (Ie), though the yields in both the cases were poor.

The methoxyisocoumarins IIb and IIc dissolved on warming with aq. NaOH by opening of the lactonic ring and on acidification furnished the corresponding ketones IIIb and IIIc respectively which cyclodehydrated on keeping with aq. 90% sulphuric acid to give the original isocoumarins IIb and IIc. The hydroxyisocoumarin IIa however did not furnish the ketone IIIa by this procedure. The product obtained is assigned the constitution of 2,3-dimethyl-4-carboxy-6-hydroxybenzofuran(V) by considering that the intermediate formed by treatment with aq. NaOH cyclodehydrates on acidification by condensing with the phenolic —OH in the position ortho to the side chain. Demethylation of the isocoumarin IIb with hydriodic acid and acetic anhydride, instead of furnishing the isocoumarin IIa also gave the same compound V as shown by mixed m.p. of the two. In this case along with demethylation of the methoxy groups, the cleavage of the lactonic ring takes place probably due to protonation with simultaneous nucleophilic attack of the phenolic —OH (formed by demethylation) on the carbonium ion that is being liberated. No ketone derivatives IIIc was obtained from the hydroxyisocoumarin IIc by treatment with aq. NaOH and subsequent acidification. The product that is formed is not assigned definite constitution as there is difficulty in getting it pure. The methoxyisocoumarin IIb readily formed the corresponding isoquinolone IVb by treatment with ethanolic ammonia (a characteristic reaction of the isocoumarins^{3a}) but the methoxyisocoumarin IIc, by a similar reaction gave the ketone IIIc instead of the corresponding isoquinolone IVc. Action of ethanolic ammonia on hydroxyisocoumarins did not furnish the pure isoquinolones. (±) 4,6-Dimethoxy- α -methylhomophthalic acid(VI) which would be a good intermediate for achieving synthesis of other isocoumarins was obtained by oxidation of the ketone IIIb with sodium hypobromite. It was also obtained directly from the isocoumarin IIb by dissolving it in aq. NaOH by warming and then treating with NaOBr.

It can be concluded from the present and previous work;^{1,2} that the yield of 3,4-dimethylisocoumarins from α -methylacetyl esters is definitely superior to that of 4-methylisocoumarins obtained from the corresponding acetyl esters¹ by cyclodehydration in presence of conc. H₂SO₄. One of the major factors which would boost the yield of isocoumarins in this reaction is the retardation of the competing reaction of hydrolysis of the

3. (a) H. E. Ungnade, D. V. Nightingale and H. E. French, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1945, **10**, 533.

(b) R. D. Haworth, H. K. Pindred and P. R. Jefferies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3617.

AAC' Mechanism

esters and that suggests that the hydrolysis may be taking place by AAC' type of mechanism.^{4,5} It is a known fact that conc. H_2SO_4 promotes this type of mechanism⁵ and the electron attracting $-\text{COCH}_3$ group in the ester part of the molecule of these esters would greatly facilitate the acyl cleavage. The rate of hydrolysis of the acetyl ester ($\text{R} = \text{H}$) would then be greater than that of α -methylacetyl ester ($\text{R} = \text{Me}$) of the same acid due to the presence of the electron repelling—Me group in the ester part of the molecule in the latter case which would retard the acyl cleavage and so the hydrolysis. If the amount of the acid formed in a cyclodehydration reaction of the acetyl and α -methylacetyl esters of the same acid is taken as criterion for the rate of hydrolysis then it lends a direct experimental support to consider this hydrolysis to be of AAC' type e.g. in the cyclodehydration reaction 1.5 g. of *m*-methoxybenzoic acid was isolated from 3.0 g. of its acetyl

4. C. K. Ingold "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", (Cornell University Press, 1953) p. 769.

5. E. S. Gould "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", (Holt, Reinhart and Winston N.Y. 1959) p. 325.

ester¹ while only 0.2 g. of the same acid as isolated from 3.0 g. of its α -methylacetyl ester² under the same conditions. It is interesting to note that α -methylacetyl ester of trimethyl ether of gallic acid (Id) and of 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid (If) cyclodehydrated to give the corresponding 3, 4-dimethylisocoumarins but the corresponding acetyl esters have been reported to fail.^{1,3b} This can now be attributed to the fact that in the former case the cyclodehydration could proceed to some extent because the competing reaction of hydrolysis was slow while in the latter case the hydrolysis was too fast compared to the cyclodehydration which in both the cases is sterically hindered due to the presence of $-\text{OCH}_3$ group in position 3.

U. V. spectra of all isocoumarins are recorded. Their U. V. curves are similar to those obtained for the corresponding 4-methylisocoumarins.¹

EXPERIMENTAL

General method for preparation of α -methylacetyl esters of the acids: A mixture of the acid (*), 1-bromoethyl methyl ketone⁶ (6 g.), potassium carbonate (3.2 g), methanol (80 ml) and water (8 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 17 hr. It was then cooled and filtered to remove KBr. Methanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue after washing with aq. NaHCO_3 was extracted with ether, washed well with water, distilled or crystallised as the case may be. (All these esters get readily hydrolysed in presence of cold aq. NaOH).

(\pm) α -Methylacetyl 3, 5-dihydroxy benzoate (Ia): from α -resorcylic acid (5.4 g.). It was crystallised from benzene-alcohol mixture as prisms, m.p. 140-141°; yield 4.2 g. (first crystallisation m.p. 136-39°) (Found C, 59.2, H, 5.7; $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 58.9, H, 5.4%).

(\pm) α -Methylacetyl 3, 5-dimethoxybenzoate (Ib): from 3,5-dimethoxybenzoic acid⁷ (7.2 g.). It distilled at 150-54°/0.7 mm.; yield 5.4 g. (Found C, 62.2, H, 6.7.; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 62.15 and H, 6.5%).

(\pm) α -Methylacetyl 3, 4,5-trihydroxybenzoate (Ic): from gallic acid (6.8 g.). An oily substance obtained initially, crystallised from ethyl acetate petrol ether (40-60°) as needle clusters m.p. 187-188°; yield 4.0 g. (first crystallisation gives m.p. 182-184°) (Found C, 55.0, H, 4.9; $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 55.0 and H, 5.0%).

(\pm) α -Methylacetyl 3, 4, 5-trimethoxybenzoate (Id): from 3, 4, 5-trimethoxybenzoic acid⁸ (8.4 g.). It distilled at 156-160°/0.25 mm.; yield 7.0 g. (Found C, 59.6, H, 6.6; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 59.58, H, 6.38%).

(\pm) α -Methylacetyl 3-hydroxy-6-methylbenzoate (Ie): from 3-hydroxy-6-methylbenzoic acid⁹ (6.6 g.). It distilled at 170-175°/0.6 mm.; m.p. 67-70°; yield 7.5 g. It

*The quantity is specified under each ester.

6. J. R. Catch, D. F. Eliot, D. H. Hey and E. R. H. Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 272.

7. C. Bullow and G. Riess, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 3901; G. D. Graves and R. Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2452.

8. F. Manthner, *Organic Synthesis*, Coll. Vol. I., p. 522.

9. O. Jacobsen, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 1963; vide O. Baudisch and W. H. Perkin *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 1883.

crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture as prisms m.p. 69-70° (Found C, 64.5; H, 6.1; $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 64.8; H, 6.3%).

(±) α -*Methylacetyl 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoate* (If): from 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid⁹ (6.64 g.). It distilled at 128-130°/0.6 mm; yield 6 g (Found C, 65.8; H, 6.8%; $C_{13}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 66.1 and H, 6.78%).

5,7-Dihydroxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (IIa): The ester Ia (2 g.) was well mixed with cold 90% H_2SO_4 (18 ml.) at 0-5° and was kept at this temperature for 3 hr. (A dark green solution was obtained) and then poured over crushed ice. The product crystallised from aq. ethanol as shining scales, m p. 269-270°; yield 1.5 g. (crude yield 1.75 g.) (Found C, 64.2; H, 5.2; $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.1; H, 4.9%). U. V. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} 242, 365 m μ (log ϵ , 4.34 and 3.64).

5,7-Diacetoxy-3, 4-dimethylisocoumarin was prepared by acetylating the isocoumarin IIa (0.3 g.) by refluxing with acetic anhydride (5 ml) in presence of pyridine (4 drops) for 3 hr. and then pouring on ice cold acidulated water. It crystallised from ethyl acetate as cubes, m p. 127-128°; yield 0.25 g. (Found C, 62.2, H, 5.2; $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 62.1 and H, 4.86%).

Action of aq. NaOH on the isocoumarin IIa: 2,3-dimethyl-4-carboxy-6-hydroxybenzofuran (V): The isocoumarin IIa (0.5 g.) was dissolved in aq. NaOH (5 ml.; 10%). The solution was kept aside at room temperature for half an hour and then acidified with conc. HCl. The product crystallised from dilute ethanol, as needles m p. 230-233°; yield 0.4 g. (Found C, 64.2, H, 4.8; $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.1 and H, 4.9%).

5,7-Dimethoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (IIb): The ester Ib (2 g.) was well mixed with 90% H_2SO_4 (18 ml) and was kept aside at room temperature (a green coloured solution was formed) for 3 hr. and then poured over crushed ice. The product after washing with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and then with water, was crystallised from dilute ethanol as needles m.p. 115-116°, yield 1.4 g. (crude yield 1.6 g.) Found C, 66.9; H, 6.4; $C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 66.6; H, 6.0%; U.V. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} 242, 262, 360 m μ , log ϵ 4.24, 4.08, 3.76).

(±) α -*Methyl- α -(2-carboxy-4, 6-dimethoxyphenyl) acetone* (IIIb): The isocoumarin IIb (1 g.) was heated with aq. NaOH (10 ml., 10%) for 3 hr. on boiling water bath and the clear solution obtained was acidified with conc. HCl. The pasty product slowly solidified on scratching. It crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture as needles, m p 129-131°; yield 0.83 g. (Found C, 62.5; H, 6.6; $C_{13}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 62.15 and H, 6.37%).

This ketone (IIIb) (0.3 g) on keeping with 90% H_2SO_4 (5 ml.) at room temperature for 17 hr. and then pouring on crushed ice furnished *5,7-dimethoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin* (IIb). It crystallised from aq. ethanol as needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen 115-116°, yield 0.2 g.

5,7-Dimethoxy-3,4-dimethylisoquinolone (IVb): Ethanolic solution of the isocoumarin IIb (0.3 g., in 10 ml of ethanol) was mixed with liquor ammonia (20 ml.) and was heated on boiling water bath for 3 hr. with the addition of more of ammonia (in all 20 ml.)

from time to time. The reaction was kept at room temperature overnight after adding more of ammonia (10 ml.). Ethanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the solution was boiled off to drive residual ammonia. The solid that separated on cooling crystallised from ethyl acetate as plates, m.p. 233-234°, yield 0.1 g (Found C, 67.1; H, 6.8 and N, 5.9%; $C_{13}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 66.9; H, 6.5 and N, 6.0%).

Demethylation of the isocoumarin IIb: 2,3-Dimethyl-4-carboxy-6-hydroxybenzofuran (V): The isocoumarin IIb (0.4 g.) was heated with hydriodic acid (10 ml., 57%) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) in an oil bath for 2 hr. at 130–140° and then poured over crushed ice to which aq. $NaHSO_3$ was added. The solid product after washing with aq. $NaHSO_3$, was crystallised from aq. ethanol as shining needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen (obtained from IIa) 232-233°, yield 0.12 g.

(±) *4,6-Dimethoxy- α -methylhomophthalic acid (VI):* A prepared solution of ice cold sodium hypobromite (4 ml., prepared by dissolving 1.6 ml. of liquid Br_2 , in 20 ml of 20% ice cold aq. $NaOH$) was added in small portions at 10-20° with shaking (in 15 minutes) to an ice cold solution of the ketone IIIb (0.5 g.) in aq. $NaOH$ (2. ml., 10%) or alternatively to the ice-cold solution of the isocoumarin IIb (0.5 g.) in aq. $NaOH$ (10 ml., 10%) (obtained by heating on water bath for 2 hr.). The reaction mixture was then mechanically shaken at room temperature for 4 hr. A heavy layer of bromoform that separated was removed by extracting it with ether. The aq. portion on acidification gave a pasty substance which was taken in ether washed thoroughly with aq. $NaHSO_3$ and then with water. The ether was removed and the residue was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petrol ether mixture as cubes, m.p. 166-167° (decomp.); yield 0.2 g. (first crystallisation gives m.p. 162-164°) (Found C, 56.9; H, 5.5; $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 56.7 and H, 5.5 %).

5, 6, 7-Trihydroxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (IIc): The ester Ic (2 g.) was mixed with 90% H_2SO_4 (18 ml.) and was kept aside at room temperature for 3 hr. (some solid crystallised) and then poured over crushed ice. The product was treated with aq. $NaHCO_3$ to remove the acid and was quickly filtered and washed thoroughly with water. It crystallised from methanol (charcoal) as cubes, m.p. decomposes above 310°; yield 0.95 g. (crude yield 1.2 g.) (Found C, 59.8; H, 4.8; $C_{11}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 59.46; H, 4.5%). U. V. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} 255, 342 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.51 and 3.78.

Treatment of this isocoumarin with aq. $NaOH$ followed by acidification gave a product soluble in $NaHCO_3$ with m.p. 194-199° but did not crystallise well.

5,6, 7-Trimethoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (IIId): The ester Id (3 g.) was well mixed with 90% H_2SO_4 (27 ml.) and was kept at room temperature for 65 hr. (a dark coloured solution was formed) and then was poured over crushed ice. The pasty product was extracted with ether and the extract was well washed with aq. $NaHCO_3$ to remove the acid formed by hydrolysis and then washed with water. The residue, obtained after removing ether crystallised from benzene (charcoal) as shining prisms, m.p. 221-22°, yield 0.3 g. (first crystallisation gave m.p. 219-21°) (Found C, 63.3; H, 6.1; $C_{14}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 63.6, and H, 6.0%). U. V. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} 250, 337 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.6, 3.69.

5-Hydroxy-3,4,8-trimethylisocoumarin (IIe): The ester Ie (2 g.) was well mixed with 90% H_2SO_4 (18 ml.) and was kept aside at room temperature for 24 hr. (the solution became dark-red in colour) and then was poured over crushed ice. The pasty product was

trituated with aq. NaHCO_3 to remove the acid and was quickly filtered, washed well with water and was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petrol ether mixture as needles, m.p. 225-27°; yield 0.15 g. (Found C, 70.2; H, 5.8; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.5 and H, 5.9%). U. V. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} 242, 285, 362 $\text{m}\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.5, 3.87, 3.56).

5-Methoxy-3,4,8-trimethylisocoumarin (IIf): The ester If (2 g.) was well mixed with 90% H_2SO_4 (18 ml.) and was kept aside at room temperature for 48 hr. and then poured over crushed ice. The pasty product solidified slowly. After triturating it with aq. NaHCO_3 to remove the acid, it was well washed with water and was crystallised from petrol ether (60-80°) as needles, m.p. 89-90°, yield 0.5 g. (crude yield 1.2 g.) (Found C, 71.4; H, 6.7; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 71.5 and H, 6.5%). U. V. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} 235, 265, 355 $\text{m}\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.31, 4.12, 3.80).

(\pm) α -*Methyl- α -(2-carboxy-3-methyl-6-methoxyphenyl) acetone* (IIIIf): The isocoumarin IIf (0.5 g.) was heated with aq. NaOH (10 ml., 10%) on a boiling water bath for 6 hr. and the clear solution was acidified with conc. HCl . The pasty product solidified on scratching and cooling. It crystallised from benzene-petrol ether mixture as needle clusters, m.p. 106-09°, yield 0.4 g. Recrystallisation gave m.p. 110-12°, (Found C, 65.8; H, 6.7; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 66.1 and H, 6.7 %).

The same ketone IIIIf was obtained by heating on water bath a solution of the isocoumarin IIf (0.5 g.) in ethanol (10 ml.) with liquor ammonia (10 ml.) for 4 hr. with the addition of more ammonia (30 ml.) from time to time. After keeping reaction mixture overnight, alcohol and ammonia was removed by distilling under reduced pressure and the remaining solution was evaporated to dryness on water bath. The residue crystallised from benzene-petrol ether mixture repeatedly as needle clusters, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above specimen 110-112°.

The ketone IIIIf (0.2 g.) on keeping with 90% H_2SO_4 (5 ml.) at room temperature for 3 hr. and then on pouring on crushed ice furnished *5-Methoxy-3,4,8-trimethyl isocoumarin* (IIf). The product after washing with aq. NaHCO_3 was crystallised from petrol ether (60-80°) as needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen 89.90°, yield 0.11 g.

The authors offer their thanks to Shri R. S. Kulkarni for microanalyses.